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SHIPS, SHIPPING, AND SPACESHIPS: HOW US COMMERCIAL SPACE CARGO INDUSTRIES CAN AVOID THE UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES OF THE JONES ACT

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ABSTRACT

In the United States, the Jones Act (1920) requires all vessels carrying cargo between US ports to be American-built, crewed, operated, and flagged. Over a hundred years later, as cargo shipping begins to expand into outer space, American policymakers must learn from the negative unintended consequences of the Jones Act. In order to support the growth of the US industry without enacting harmful protectionist policies, the US space community must invest in multi-operational infrastructure, focus on cost-effective domestic operations, and invest early in education for American personnel to organically retain domestic expertise. This paper argues that American policymakers in the commercial space industry should avoid adopting a regulatory framework similar to the Jones Act because of its protectionist structure and its long-term industry harm.

KEYWORDS: Space Law, Maritime Law, Jones Act, Commercial Space Policy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Following the World Wars, the United States passed the Merchant Marine Act of 1920, commonly known as the Jones Act, to strengthen the maritime industry, but the protectionist nature of the policy had unintended consequences of negatively impacting maritime companies' abilities to compete globally. This paper seeks to serve as a warning that protectionist and nationalist domestic policies can be detrimental to the sustainment of commercial industries. First, this paper establishes a foundation outlining the Jones Act and its impact on the commercial maritime industry.² Next, the current US space policy is examined to help understand how the US views space operations, infrastructure, growth, and talent retention. This policy includes relevant acts passed by Congress and existing codified statutes under the United States Code. Finally, this paper creates a parallel between the maritime and space industries, highlighting the lessons that space policy should learn from the maritime industry, from the European Union, and from the impacts of the Jones Act.

In December 2025, the White House issued an executive order urging Americans to develop technologies that contribute to national "strength, security, and prosperity." One of the stated goals was "Growing a vibrant commercial space economy" by fostering economic growth, establishing "ground, space, and lunar infrastructure and standards that enable implementation of space priorities and a robust space industrial base."³ Notably, the current White House policy for the maritime industry uses very similar language, saying, "The Secretary of Commerce...shall recommend...for inclusion in the [Maritime Action Plan] all available incentives to help shipbuilders domiciled in allied nations partner to undertake capital investment in the United States to help strengthen the shipbuilding capacity of the United States."⁴ The language of the stated goals is similar, but the US government and domestic space companies must be wary of adopting protectionist regulatory frameworks.

Maritime and space are similarly situated at the cross-section of national security and commercial goods, and the US should avoid adopting a regulatory framework for space cargo transport that mirrors the protectionist structure of the Jones Act. Space cargo includes humanitarian materials, military supplies, industry parts, and medical and personal equipment.⁵ Looking forward, the US commercial space policy must invest in building a robust infrastructure capable of supporting multinational use, strengthen cost-effective domestic operations, and invest early in the retention of domestic expertise.

2. UNDERSTANDING THE JONES ACT

In the United States, the Jones Act is the controlling federal statute regulating the domestic commercial shipping industry. It requires that all vessels transporting cargo directly between two US ports are American-built, owned, crewed, and flagged.⁶ The Jones Act was passed after the First World War with the goal of strengthening national security and protecting domestic maritime operations. At the time,

² Merchant Marine Act of 1920 (Jones Act), Pub. L. No. 66-261, § 27, 41 Stat. 988 (1920)

³ The White House. (2025, December 18). *Ensuring American space superiority*. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/12/ensuring-american-space-superiority/>.

⁴ The White House. (2025, April 9). *Restoring America's Maritime Dominance*. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/04/restoring-americas-maritime-dominance/>.

⁵ Walton, R. O., & Goehlich, R. A. (2022). *Space cargo: Ultra-fast delivery on Earth—Potential of using suborbital space vehicles for the transportation of cargo*. *International Journal of Aviation, Aeronautics, and Aerospace*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.15394/ijaaa.2022.1671>.

⁶ Wicker, Sen. R., Cantwell, Sen. M., DeFazio, Rep. P., & Graves, Rep. S. (2020, June 5). *Why the Jones Act is still needed 100 years later*. *Defense News*. <https://www.defensenews.com/opinion/commentary/2020/06/05/why-the-jones-act-is-still-needed-100-years-later/>.

those fears were well-founded: the merchant marine fleet was a key component of national security and economic prosperity.⁷ Decades later, many believe the Jones Act stunted US maritime growth.

2.1. Jones Act Impact on US Commercial Shipping

Following the Second World War, the US dominated global shipping, operating a fleet of more than 5,500 ships. At the time, national security was at the forefront of the American mind, and the US had the industry, resources, and knowledge to rule the high seas. In less than one-hundred years, US shipping dropped to 22nd among global fleets of merchant vessels. The obvious explanation for the decline is strict standards and cost: it is significantly more expensive to build, register, and crew vessels in the US.⁸ But the benefits of maintaining a US fleet are four-fold:

- US vessels meet both commercial and national defense standards;
- Seafarers maintain a standard of expertise and excellence;
- Domestic shipyards contribute to national security; and
- Intermodal transportation infrastructure is maintained for commercial and defense purposes.⁹

2.2. Benefits of the Jones Act in the United States

The Jones Act is critical for US stability in the maritime industry. Under its standards, American mariners have been able to maintain more than 650,000 jobs within the US, culminating in a \$150 billion contribution to the economy each year.¹⁰ A thriving shipbuilding industry also allows for technologically modern warships to be constructed entirely within the United States, supporting national defense goals and maintaining industrial integrity. In essence, “[W]ith 97 percent of all U.S. overseas commerce being conducted by foreign-flagged carriers, [l]osing the Jones Act would mean ceding our domestic maritime economy to China and other foreign-flagged competitors, making us more vulnerable during times of crisis.”¹¹ Maintaining vertical chains of operation within the US helps control security measures and supports local economies while boosting American workers and retaining domestic industrial expertise.

2.3. Negative Impacts of the Jones Act in the United States

The commercial space industry must understand where Jones Act policies went wrong to avoid the same pitfalls in future domestic space policy. The Jones Act deserves criticism because it lost its practicality in a world that became increasingly reliant on globalization and multinational operation. In practice, the restrictions imposed by the Jones Act, combined with a failure of foresight by the US government, led to the decline of the domestic maritime industry. Requiring all operations to take place in the US led to higher shipping rates and lower demand for shipping services.¹² The US failed to invest in mariners at the rate required to efficiently and effectively keep up with the global market. Unintended consequences of the Jones Act created unavoidable costs: the cost of the necessity of requiring a US-built maritime service, the cost of operating that fleet, and the cost of retaining a merchant fleet.

⁷ Mercogliano, S. (2019, December 1). *Sea History 169—Winter 2019-2020: A Century of the Jones Act*. National Maritime Historical Society & Sea History Magazine, 169, 13. https://issuu.com/seahistory/docs/sh_169_winter-2019-20/15.

⁸ *Supra*, note 7.

⁹ American Maritime Partnership. (2017, October 17). *Jones Act: Cornerstone of U.S. maritime safety and security*. <https://www.americanmaritimepartnership.com/u-s-maritime-industry/jones-act-overview/>.

¹⁰ *Supra*, note 9.

¹¹ *Ibid*.

¹² Grabow, C., Manak, I., & Ikenson, D. J. (2018, June 28). *The Jones Act: A burden America can no longer bear*. Cato Institute. <https://www.cato.org/publications/policy-analysis/jones-act-burden-america-can-no-longer-bear>.

Cost of Necessity. One of the major unintended consequences of the Jones Act is the inflated cost to build an American ship. A coastwise vessel used for Jones Act cargo transport built in the US typically costs between \$190-250 million dollars to build. A similar foreign-built vessel costs about \$30 million. Due to high construction costs, US merchant vessels are, on average, 11 years older than similar vessels in other countries' fleets. In contrast, the Chinese started constructing dual-use (military and cargo) vessels, likely providing a significant strategic advantage should a future conflict arise.¹³

US vessels that do not participate in the Jones Act trade are not required to be US-built, and yet they are still successful. In fact, 30 of 46 vessels in the US Ready Reserve Fleet, ships available for the US government in the event of armed conflict, are foreign constructed vessels.¹⁴ Since the US industry faces challenges with waterborne transportation due to Jones Act restrictions, many companies increasingly turn to other modes of transportation. The result is significantly increased transportation and shipping costs. In 2013, it was estimated that traffic congestion cost the US economy nearly \$124 billion, expected to rise by more than \$60 billion in 2030. Even incremental increases in the use of Jones Act vessels could significantly and positively contribute to the US economy.¹⁵

Cost of Operation. The US failed to keep pace with foreign shipbuilding and vessel operation because it failed to adapt its market to match international practices that ultimately allow for more cost-effective processes. Overall, US vessels are significantly more expensive to build and operate than foreign vessels. Domestic shipbuilding reduced dramatically because "Subsidies that compensated for escalating costs in domestic production were withdrawn, leading to the collapse of the commercial shipbuilding industry." Labor and raw materials are also more expensive at US shipyards than at comparable foreign shipyards.¹⁶ Higher costs of operation lead to a reduced demand for shipping services and vessel operators meaning, "Transportation expenses – incurred to move raw materials and intermediate goods to the next stage in the production...comprise a significant portion of the cost of goods...elevated transportation costs affect nearly every business in every industry."¹⁷ US crews are more expensive because of pay requirements, vessel and personnel insurance costs, and heightened regulatory requirements from the US Coast Guard. In 2010, a study by the Maritime Administration reported that operating a US Jones Act-compliant vessel was 2.7 times more expensive than a similar vessel from a foreign competitor. Daily costs for foreign ships averaged \$7,500, while the US vessel required more than \$20,000.¹⁸

Beyond operating expenses, national security goals also contribute to the cost of US vessels. Overreach of government regulation in shipbuilding due to national security concerns allowed the government to micromanage the design and execution of major shipbuilding programs. Ultimately, changes are costly and can cause significant production delays, meaning, "One distinguishing characteristic of this culture is a shared responsibility between shipyards and combat systems integrators...this requires extensive coordination in design and production, which results in significant overhead spread across all builders' contracts."¹⁹ Increased costs forced American companies to look outside the US to meet production needs.

¹³ Salisbury, Emma. (2025, January 27). *Don't Protect the U.S. Merchant Marine—Promote It*. War on the Rocks. <https://warontherocks.com/2025/01/dont-protect-the-u-s-merchant-marine-promote-it/>.

¹⁴ *Supra*, note 13.

¹⁵ *Ibid*.

¹⁶ Dur, R. A. P. A. (2025, February). *The high costs of doing (shipbuilding) business | proceedings - February 2025* vol. 151/2/1,464. U.S. Naval Institute. <https://www.usni.org/magazines/proceedings/2025/february/high-costs-doing-shipbuilding-business>.

¹⁷ Grabow, C., Manak, I., Ikenson, D. (2018, June 28). *The Jones Act: A Burden American Can No Longer Bear*. Cato Institute. <https://www.cato.org/publications/policy-analysis/jones-act-burden-america-can-no-longer-bear#introduction>.

¹⁸ *Supra*, note 17.

¹⁹ *Supra*, Note 16.

Cost of Retention. The US merchant mariner fleet is shrinking. Depletion of the US fleet created a major reduction in available licensed US mariners, thus weakening the US disaster or emergency response should a conflict arise.²⁰ Multiple leaders from the Maritime Administration and the Department of Defense have testified before Congress that a major institutional concern is a growing shortage of US mariners. An inadequate mariner force is both an economic and a national security risk, albeit an avoidable one. Lack of investment into recruiting akin to that for uniformed US services, combined with high barriers to entry and a lack of public recognition for service, have all contributed to a depletion of the mariner fleet, resulting in a loss of investment, talent, and expertise.²¹ When industries are not committed to domestic professionals, foreign actors are able to gain momentum.

Sal Mercogliano from Campbell University explained, “It is easy to write off the American merchant marine as too expensive and outdated due to the Jones Act. But the question needs to be asked: Is the United States prepared to outsource its coastwise trade and lose the majority of its remaining deep-draft merchant ships? Such a loss may provide short-term economic benefit, but the long-term danger and threat to national security may prove fatal. This was the concern echoed a hundred years ago, and it remains as pertinent today as it did then.”²² If this is the one-hundred-year concern for maritime shipping, then it is a concern that commercial space cannot ignore in its next one-hundred years.

3. AVOIDING POLICY PITFALLS IN COMMERCIAL SPACE

The similarities between the growing space industry and the maritime industry are too close to ignore. Both industries base their business models on moving objects between distant locations, so both must conduct their operations at a scale large enough to generate profit and function under complex regulatory schemes.²³ In the maritime realm and in outer space, sophisticated and complex vehicles are necessary to transport goods. Whether the goods are basic cargo like pharmaceuticals or advanced machinery parts for building a base on the moon, the vehicle to move those products is equally sophisticated. That level of engineering requires dedicated and talented personnel in construction and operation. It is understandable why the policymakers who enacted the Jones Act would want to protect American industry at all costs to promote the US development of these technologies. But the Jones Act took protectionism too far by creating a system that rejected globalization and unsustainably raised costs.

The major lessons the space industry must learn from the Jones Act include rejecting purely domestic operations in the United States by instead investing in building a robust, globally functional infrastructure, focusing on cost-effective domestic operations that allow US-based companies to remain profitable while operating in the United States, and investing early in education and incentivizing the retention of domestic experience and expertise.

3.1. *Current Status of the Outer Space Commercial Goods Industry*

Commercial space delivery networks are growing, with companies like SpaceX and Blue Origin leading the march toward affordable and reusable space freight. While technology is evolving, the US must begin to consider how it will regulate the emerging market.²⁴ Initial space cargo deliveries will likely focus on industrial, humanitarian, military, and medical needs. More robust commercial space efforts will likely

²⁰ *Supra*, Note 17.

²¹ gCaptain. (2024, September 22). *Op-ed: U.S. merchant mariner shortage demands action now*. <https://gcaptain.com/op-ed-u-s-merchant-mariner-shortage-demands-action-now/>.

²² *Supra*, note 6.

²³ *Commercial activities from the open ocean to Outer Space*. ESPI. (2018, May 23). <https://www.espi.eu/briefs/commercial-activities-from-the-open-ocean-to-outer-space/>.

²⁴ *Supra*, note 23.

center on “resource acquisition, energy production, and advanced manufacturing.”²⁵ In addition, the space mining market is predicted to be worth billions of dollars over the next decade.²⁶ Like the maritime industry, space operators will be required to transport goods that are critical for both commercial and national security purposes. Balancing the prioritization of a US-based launch vehicle with cost-effective regulatory allowances will encourage companies to maintain US-based systems that can serve a global customer.

3.2. Existing Legal Frameworks for Commercial Space Cargo

Regulators working on space issues must not allow the protectionist policies of the Jones Act to bleed into space policy. Ultimately, the federal regulation of space has been in development for decades. Key offices like the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the Department of Commerce address space regulatory concerns. The FAA Office of Commercial Space Transportation is the leading governmental framework in the US for space cargo, responsible for overseeing and regulating space transportation operations, including licensing for launch vehicles.²⁷

In 1984, Congress passed the Commercial Space Launch Act, creating regulations for licensure and launch activities.²⁸ This eventually evolved into the US Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act. Passed in 2015, the Act addresses issues impacting aerospace entrepreneurship and licensure.²⁹ Space activities are also guided by 51 USC Ch 509, the current US regulatory framework for Commercial Space Launch Activities.³⁰ Specifically, §50901 discusses issues like developing competitive US launch vehicles, investing in a strong domestic infrastructure, and encouraging private participation in space transportation services. The foundations are laid for a prosperous balance between aggressive growth in technological advancement and a strong regulatory framework. But §50919 outlines approvals and relationships between the US and other countries. While the language is not particularly protectionist yet, this is the section of the code that must be highlighted. The US should resist introducing language akin to that in the Jones Act to these relevant sections of space policy so that space players in the US are not stifled by stricter US requirements.

For inspiration, the US can look to policies being created in the European Union (EU). The European Space Policy Institute (ESPI) Executive Brief No. 23 independently calls for regulation of commercial space inspired by the maritime industry. The ESPI specifically makes the distinction between international and maritime space policy in that international relations today are more cooperative, while the demand for space resources is not yet as well-established. In section two of the ESPI, the EU highlights that actors at sea and in space, “Conduct their business activities around the commercialisation of resources/products” from distant locations, and “[c]onduct their business activities in locations outside the national jurisdiction of their countries of incorporation where the relevant international law and

²⁵ Mitchell, N. (2025, April 14). *Space commerce: Face the risk, seize the opportunities*. The Space Review: Space commerce: face the risk, seize the opportunities. <https://www.thespacereview.com/article/4968/1>.

²⁶ GetNews. (2026, January 12). *Space mining market to reach USD 7.39 billion by 2031, driven by rising demand for rare-earth metals and lunar resource extraction trends – Mordor Intelligence*. Barchart. <https://www.barchart.com/story/news/37009411/space-mining-market-to-reach-usd-7-39-billion-by-2031-driven-by-rising-demand-for-rare-earth-metals-and-lunar-resource-extraction-trends-mordor-intelligence>.

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ U.S. Congress. (1983). *H.R. 3942: Commercial Space Launch Act (98th Congress)*. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/98th-congress/house-bill/3942/text>.

²⁹ U.S. Congress. (2015). *H.R. 2262: U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act (114th Congress)*. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/house-bill/2262/text>.

³⁰ *Commercial space launch activities*, 51 U.S.C. §§ 50901–50923 (2023). <https://www.govinfo.gov/app/details/USCODE-2023-title51/USCODE-2023-title51-subtitleV-chap509/context>.

regulations are not yet highly defined.”³¹ Taking inspiration from ESPI can encourage future US policy to maintain a global perspective.

3.3. *Infrastructure Lessons for Outer Space*

US based infrastructure is rooted in national security concerns and a desire to protect the US shipbuilding industry. But the Jones Act requirement to insulate operations ultimately led to significantly higher costs. In policy reports from the White House, the administration noted that operational efficiency would increase and launch costs would decrease if the US invested in space launch infrastructure. To maintain leadership in the space sector, the US must “enable market access for United States industry,” as well as “encourage interoperability among United States, allied, and partner space systems, services, and data.”³²

Although there is no dedicated US space cargo port yet, it is important to set a precedent now that US cargo travelling between the US mainland on Earth and a future spaceport should be allowed to be carried by foreign-owned spacecraft. This opens US space infrastructure without the restrictions imposed on the maritime industry by the Jones Act. But for national and public safety purposes, these activities must be closely monitored. If the US fails to establish itself as a major spaceport now, it is likely that other countries in one-hundred years could out-produce the US in space logistics. Looking forward, the protection of critical systems and supporting infrastructure allows the US to maintain space security while avoiding the perils of protectionism.

3.4. *Cost Considerations for Space Growth*

The space industry is not immune to the push and pull of market supply and demand fluctuations. If the US wants to avoid the fate of its maritime industry, where US ships are being outpriced by foreign vessels, then the US must now prioritize cost considerations of its rocket transportation fleet. The US government’s stated goals include establishing operations “in accordance with typical market-based incentives for controlling cost and optimizing return on investment.”³³ The National Space Society reported that at some point, depending on the rate of movement into space, the “number of launches over a sustained period [must be] large enough to reduce the per-launch cost to financially practicable levels.”³⁴ Investment in fully reusable commercial cargo rockets will likely be critical for reducing the cost of moving goods into space.

For reference, NASA’s space shuttle cost about \$1.5 billion to launch 27,500 kg into Low Earth Orbit – a rate that translates to \$54,000/kg. SpaceX Falcon 9 advertised in 2020 that it cost \$62 million to launch 22,800 kg into the same orbit – a cost of \$2,720/kg.³⁵ And SpaceX is not the only company tackling this problem. Several successful startups have raised significant funding in their quest to develop a fully reusable rocket with a reasonable turnaround. Now the US needs to ensure that the creation of those vehicles remains cost-effective in comparison to alternative options in other countries.

3.5. *Talent Development and Retention*

In the National Space Policy, one of the named goals is to “Develop and Retain Space Professionals.”³⁶ But the US has struggled to achieve this goal in other industries like the maritime realm. The merchant marine played a critical role in every major US conflict since the world wars, despite the public remaining

³¹ *Supra* note 23.

³² *Supra* note 4.

³³ *Supra* note 4.

³⁴ *NSS Roadmap to Space Settlement Milestone 1: Dramatically lower launch costs to orbit*. NSS. (2021, May 14). <https://nss.org/space-settlement-roadmap-1-lower-launch-costs/>.

³⁵ *Ibid* cost-effective.

³⁶ *Supra* note 4.

unaware of mariners' contributions. Unfortunately, high barriers to entry and a lack of support for improvement in shipboard quality-of-life led to low enrollment and low retention of trained US mariners.

The space industry must pay attention to this trend. By investing in innovative commercial, civil, and national security programs, the US could establish its own pool of experienced and knowledgeable space professionals. As outlined in the US National Space Policy guidelines, the US must begin to promote and expand space careers, including investing in educational programs. The US must look beyond engineers and operators as future space operations will require geoscientists, cybersecurity experts, human-factors specialists, policy and regulatory interpreters, and more. Early and dedicated investment into both special knowledge of the space technical field and the impact on human interaction with those systems across disciplines will help the US to develop and retain its space professionals.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the US space industry is at a critical point in its development. Technology is starting to take massive strides toward the intersection of operational feasibility and affordability. But the US has been a dominant player before in the transportation industry, and it lost its steam. US merchant shipping, once a pinnacle of international cargo transportation, became too exclusionary, too expensive, and overall, too unattractive to maintain a global lead.

By establishing the foundation of the Jones Act and exploring how its requirements had unintended negative consequences in the maritime industry, space policymakers can understand how the emerging commercial space transportation industry is analogous to the maritime realm in regard to the domestic construction and operation of vehicles. In addition to both industries moving goods from one location to another, both industries also rely heavily on sophisticated vehicles created by talented individuals. Space actors must recognize the importance of talent retention and infrastructure investment. By looking at existing space policy, policymakers can be cautioned against creating regulations that stray into the same pitfalls as the Jones Act.

While the space industry is now exciting and enticing, it is the longevity that will ultimately matter in the future. US regulations must adapt to evolution in space technology through a lens of protecting US operations while maintaining a competitive global advantage. If the US wants to be the leader for the next century in space cargo transportation, it must learn from the Jones Act. Active participation in international cooperation and early investment in efficient domestic infrastructure are critical for industry growth. More importantly, that growth must account for globalization and international participation from its inception. Perhaps the US space industry can avoid the same fate suffered by the maritime realm.